

Development of a Wound Healing Cream from *Lawsonia Inermis L.* and *Allium Cepa L.*

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Abstract

This research explores the potential of *Lawsonia inermis* L. (henna) and *Allium cepa* L. (onion) in wound healing by extracting and analyzing their phytochemical compositions and evaluating their antimicrobial properties. Both plants have been traditionally used for medicinal purposes due to their wound healing and antimicrobial properties. The process involved sequential extraction, phytochemical analysis, thin-layer chromatography (TLC), and antimicrobial assays to identify the presence of various bioactive compounds and their effectiveness against common pathogens. Results indicated a significant abundance of these compounds, particularly in methanol extracts, suggesting their potential in wound healing and antibacterial applications. TLC profiling revealed distinct chemical bands, confirming the presence of specific compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, phenols, steroids, saponins, and terpenoids in both *Lawsonia inermis* and *Allium cepa*. *Lawsonia inermis* showed inhibition zones of 8.95 mm against *E. coli* and 9.44 mm against *Staphylococcus aureus*, while *Allium cepa* exhibited 8.24 mm against *E. coli* and 12.67 mm against *Staphylococcus aureus*. These results indicate strong antibacterial activity, supporting their potential in wound healing applications. The study also involved the formulation of wound healing creams, with the most effective formulation demonstrating a balanced combination of these extracts. This research offers valuable insights into the phytochemical profiles and antimicrobial properties of *Lawsonia inermis* and *Allium cepa*, supporting their use in the development of effective wound healing creams.

Keywords: *Wound healing, Lawsonia inermis L., Allium cepa L., Phytochemicals, Antimicrobial*